

CULTURAL TRANSFER THROUGH THE TRANSLATIONS OF TWO BALKAN WRITERS' NOVELS WRITTEN IN ENGLISH

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This paper focuses on the works of two Balkan writers, Elif Shafak and Kapka Kasabova, and their translation into Romanian. The two authors, of Turkish and Bulgarian origin, respectively, write their novels in English. Following the Cultural Transfer Approach as the main method of investigation, the current research dwells on the tripartite process of cultural mediation through translation.